

Reduction of Silver Borate by Hydrogen

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Reduction of silver borate by hydrogen follows the course:

The reduction is complete at 150° in about six hours and the process is prominently associated with adsorption. The extent of adsorption decreases with increase of temperature (150-400°). The uptake of hydrogen is believed to take place on silver, partly by chemisorption (through *d-s* promotion mechanism) and partly by absorption.

The present investigation is a continuation of our previous work with other metal borates.¹ With the borates of copper, nickel, and cobalt the reduction generally follows the course:

The reducibility of the above borates by hydrogen was more or less comparable to the corresponding oxides. From the known properties of silver oxide, it was therefore expected that silver borate would be reduced by hydrogen at rather low temperatures. This was found to be experimentally true, and this system offered an opportunity to study the activated adsorption more conveniently.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Silver Borate.—Dry methods are not so convenient for synthesis of silver borate having a definite composition. In wet methods also, unless great care is taken regarding the concentration of solution and conditions of experiment, products having varying compositions are obtained.

For the present investigation, silver borate was obtained by metathesis from saturated solution of AnalaR grade borax and molar solution of silver nitrate in the cold. Constant stirring was necessary during precipitation. The product was quickly filtered under suction and washed with 5% boric acid solution, and finally once with distilled water. It was carefully dried at room temperature in a vacuum desiccator for a week and finally at 40° for 6 to 8 hours in dark. The product conformed to the composition AgBO_2 (Found: B, 7.3, 7.1; Ag, 70.1, 71.5. Calc. for AgBO_2 : B, 7.2; Ag, 71.6%). The silver borate should be kept in the dark.

1. This *Journal*, 1961, 38, 7, *et seq.*

Reduction.—The apparatus was the same as that described by Khundkar². A weighed amount of the silver borate was taken in a platinum boat and placed in the reaction temperature zone in a closed system, which had earlier been evacuated and filled with purified hydrogen at atmospheric pressure. The uptake of hydrogen was followed by noting the decrease in gas volume at different intervals of time; these volumes were corrected for N. T. P. and plotted against time in Fig. 1. The water vapour formed during the reaction was absorbed in P₂O₅, taken in a small boat at the exit (cooler) end of the reaction tube.

The solid products of reduction were free B₂O₃, metallic silver, and unreduced silver borate, if any. When the product was heated with water, (the unchanged) silver borate completely hydrolyzed to silver oxide and boric acid.

The residue from the aqueous extract containing metallic silver and silver oxide was treated with dilute aqueous ammonia which dissolved only the silver oxide; from this, the amount of unreduced silver borate was calculated. The residual metallic silver was dissolved in nitric acid and determination of silver in this gave the extent of reduction.

DISCUSSION

The volume of hydrogen consumed (corrected to N. T. P.) at different temperatures (150-400°) have been plotted in Fig. 1. The same amount of silver borate was taken for each experiment so that the curves were on a comparative basis. The volume of hydrogen required for reduction of this amount of silver borate (viz. 0.2 g.) to silver and boric oxide, according to the equation,

can be calculated to be 14.9 ml. The free energy change of the above reaction was calculated to be -364 Kcal. The reduction should thus be complete at a relatively low temperature. This was confirmed by our results of analysis of the products of reduction. At all temperatures between 150° and 400°, formation of metallic silver was virtually quantitative. Any reaction between hydrogen and boric oxide in this range of temperature is improbable. Thus, at all temperatures under study, hydrogen consumption for reduction would be 14.9 ml. As the total uptake of gas was much higher than this, the progress was assumed to be accompanied by adsorption of the metal.

Nature of Curves at Different Temperatures

With the knowledge that the same volume of hydrogen is required for reduction at different temperatures, the total gas consumption values and the progress of hydrogen consumption provide interesting and useful information. Although from the curves (Fig. 1) hydrogen consumption appears stepwise, a closer scrutiny shows that the processes are not distinctly consecutive, particularly at lower temperatures.

FIG. 1. Uptake of Hydrogen by Silver Borate at different temperatures.

Taking the curve for 150°, the initial consumption of hydrogen is rather rapid, *i.e.*, about 25 ml in about 60 minutes. This is much more than the total hydrogen needed for reduction (14.9 ml). Thus at this temperature, adsorption starts right from the beginning.

At 200°, the hydrogen consumption was slower. The rate of reduction in such system could be slowed down only by fusion of the borate; this is not possible at such a low temperature. By increase of temperature from 150° to 200°, rate of reduction should somewhat increase. In the present system this increase is more than offset by the decrease in the adsorption; so that the overall hydrogen uptake is less.

This behaviour is further repeated at 300°, when the initial hydrogen consumption is smaller still. The curve for 400° appears more interesting; at this temperature, there is virtually no adsorption in the initial stage and the gas consumption appears almost entirely to be due to the reduction. The system consumes about 15-16 ml of the gas rapidly after which there is no change for over two hours; after this again, rapid uptake of gas begins.

From a study of the above curves, following observations may be made:

(a) Reduction of silver borate by hydrogen (giving metallic silver and B_2O_3) is complete in the temperature range 150°-400°. The process is associated with adsorption of hydrogen, presumably on the silver surface. In fact, adsorption is the more prominent feature of the system.

(b) At 150°, adsorption takes place from the beginning. At higher temperatures, there is an induction period for the adsorption, which becomes longer with increase of temperature.

(c) The reactions were carried out for the same period at different temperatures. It was found that the total hydrogen adsorbed decreased with increase of temperature. The total gas adsorbed has been taken from the total gas uptake less 14.9 ml (that reqd. for reduction of 0.2 g. AgBO_2) for each temperature.

Behaviour of Precipitated Silver

In the preceding section it was seen that the experimental observations could be explained only on the basis of considerable adsorption of hydrogen on metallic silver. Although silver has been used as a catalyst, information from direct experimental evidence of adsorption of hydrogen on silver surface is surprisingly confusing. Sieverts and Hagenacker³ and Steacie and Johnson⁴ observed that below 400°, no measurable amounts of hydrogen was taken up by silver. Durau⁵ observed that at 18° (760 mm) hydrogen was reversibly taken up by silver and that it covered 5.7% of the available silver surface. According to Drake and Benton⁶ hydrogen is chemisorbed on bare silver surfaces at temperatures above 300°, which could be removed by evacuation. Silver is also believed by Moeller⁷ to form a hydride, Ag-H . Pietsch and Seieferling⁸ described formation of a solid silver hydride.

For comparing our results, adsorption of hydrogen was also studied on a sample of silver powder (precipitated silver, containing 99.5% Ag, B. D. H.). An examination of curves in Fig. 2. indicates the following:

FIG. 2. Uptake of hydrogen by precipitated silver at different temperatures.

3. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, **68**, 115.
4. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, **117A** 662.
5. *Z. physik*, 1926, **37**, 419.
6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 506.
7. "Inorganic Chemistry", John Wiley, 1954.
8. *Naturwiss.*, 1931, **19**, 573.

(a) With precipitated silver at 300°, induction period is about 160 minutes; with silver borate also, the second stage of the hydrogen uptake started after about 150 minutes. For both cases, the induction period at 400° is longer and the total adsorption less.

(b) For experiments with silver borate at 300° and 400°, the product (silver) formed was not finely divided, but conglomerated into small bead-like masses. The precipitated silver borate did not undergo any such change after hydrogen adsorption at 300° & 400°, but remained unchanged in physical appearance.

Nature of Adsorption

It is known that chemisorption of hydrogen is largely confined to metals of the transition series, which have partly filled 'd' levels and it is believed to take place by covalence with the unpaired electrons in the 'd' level. Certain non-transition metals, specially those of Group IB, are active towards some gases. In these metals, it is thought that the *d-s* transition can take place without any great expenditure of energy and hence some 'd' levels are left unpaired and are subsequently involved in chemisorption⁹. Some workers have estimated the *d-s* promotion energy of copper and gold and found them to be low. For silver, the *d-s* promotion energy for adsorption of gases like CO and C₂H₄ have been found to be higher than copper and gold.

The factors on which the *d-s* promotion energy depends are not clearly known. It is possible that in the range of temperature studied by us an active form of silver having low *d-s* promotion energy exists and this accounted for the hydrogen adsorption. It is also possible that the silver produced from silver borate (as also the precipitated silver used) has "defect" lattices having electrons in the higher energy levels which could be involved in chemisorption.

It must be pointed out that the volume of hydrogen uptake was considerable. It can be calculated that for all the experiments, for formation of Ag-H only about 15 ml. of hydrogen would be required. The volumes of the gas adsorbed at different temperatures are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Adsorption of hydrogen on reduced silver borate and precipitated silver.

Material taken.	Volume of hydrogen (ml) adsorbed at			
	150°	200°.	300°.	400°.
AgBO ₂ reduced	46.5	37.7	35.1	18.4
Precipitated Silver	..	..	41.4	35.7

It will be seen that the maximum hydrogen adsorption is three times the volume required for the formation of hydride, Ag-H.

In copper also, chemisorption has been explained on the basis of *d-s* promotion and subsequent covalence of hydrogen with the resulting unpaired '3d' electron.

